

COPING WITH JOB INSECURITY: NARRATIVES OF CONTINGENT WORKERS

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Abstract

This study sought to explore coping strategies used by contingent workers at a multinational firm in Zimbabwe to deal with job insecurity. Ten research participants, who had worked for the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe for at least five months, were interviewed using face-to-face semi-structured interviews. The study found that contingent workers at the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe use several strategies to deal with job insecurity. The three major coping strategies that they use are organizational citizenship behaviour, deviant work behaviours and job search. Only a few research participants at the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe indicated that they utilize impression management techniques to deal with job insecurity. The current study recommends that contingent workers at the case organisation should be aware that some of the coping mechanisms that they use to deal with job insecurity are gross misconducts, which warrant direct dismissal. The study also recommends that managers at the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe should be aware of the coping mechanisms that contingent workers use to deal with job insecurity, and that they should establish intervention strategies that reduce job insecurity and improve worker employability.

Keywords: Contingent Worker, Coping, Coping Mechanisms, Job Insecurity, Multinational Firm.

JEL Classification: J22, L61, M54, O19.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several countries across the globe have been obliged to implement economic adjustment policies to salvage their shrinking economies from the macro-economic crisis of the new century (Alonso & Matea, 2023; Sgaravatti et al., 2023; Liargovas & Psychalis, 2019; Lefophane, 2024; Fapohunda, 2021; Labour Force Survey, 2022). Due to the new millennium's macro-economic crisis, countries began to implement traditional structural adjustment policies such as trade liberalization, flexible labor markets, privatization of state enterprises, and labor market deregulation to resuscitate their ailing economies (Benos et al., 2023; Darvas et al., 2023; Alonso & Matea, 2023; Kalejaiye, 2021; Okafor, 2022). Organizations had no option but to reorganize their structures and approaches to adjust to the new realities for them to remain afloat (Holland et al., 2024; Ikeije & Okpo, 2023; Kougiannou & Mendonça, 2024). Holland et al. (2024) claim that the economic crisis of the new century has forced many firms to embrace the flexible labor market, which led to the emergence of non-standard forms of work. Additionally, Mukwakwami (2021) argues that besides the economic adjustment reforms, flexible labour markets compelled organisations to consider non-standard forms of work arrangements as a cost reduction strategy compared to the job for life concept. Several researchers argue that employers utilize non-standard forms of work in a bid to reduce costs

(Brewster & Kougiannou, 2024; Mendonça, 2024; Mail & Dasan, 2023; Meacham & Chhim, 2024). Though non-standard forms of work provide workers with work flexibility, it is known that contingent workers endure a variety of difficulties and uncertainties, which include job insecurity (Anand et al., 2023; Gupta & Dhar, 2024; Muñoz Medina et al., 2023). Similarly, Chong et al. (2024) state that nonstandard forms of work have caused a sense of insecurity and workers are obliged to protect their own job security by maintaining their employability because companies are no longer able to provide stable and long-term employment.

Furthermore, Greenhalgh and Rosenblatt (2021) contend that because non-standard forms of work are replacing permanent positions, perceptions of job insecurity have also increased among permanent employees. Sverke et al. (2022) conceptualize job insecurity as a work-related stressor for concerns about one's career prospects. It is noteworthy that there is a common belief that job insecurity and the possibility of losing one's job will negatively impact an employee (Jung et al., 2021; Shin et al., 2022). In a similar vein, Veloso and Brandão (2022) assert that job insecurity affects employee attitudes and wellbeing. Scholars have contended that the threat of losing a job could motivate workers to take proactive steps to cope with this threat (Gupta & Dhar, 2024; Chong et al., 2024; De Angelis et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2022). Dewe (2019) defines coping as proactive or reactive responses to a dangerous circumstance intended to lessen the threat or ease the discomfort.

Muñoz Medina et al. (2023) argue that strategies that workers use to cope with job insecurity influence adjustment to this stressful situation. Although job insecurity has been extensively studied in recent decades (Chambel & Ugarte, 2023; Moura & Brandão, 2022; Chong et al., 2024; De Angelis et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2022), little is known about how contingent workers deal with job insecurity. This is surprising, considering the heated debates around contingent workers' job insecurity experiences. Given the difficulties and uncertainties endured by contingent workers, there is a need for a study to explore coping mechanisms that these contingent workers use to deal with job insecurity. It is also important to note that most research on job insecurity have been conducted in the global north with few studies conducted in the global south. The aforementioned implies that there have not been many studies that relate to coping strategies that contingent workers in the global south use to deal with job insecurity. It is against this backdrop that this study was conducted to explore coping strategies that contingent workers use to deal with job insecurity at a multinational firm in Zimbabwe.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents a theory that guided this research, antecedents of job insecurity and coping mechanisms used by contingent workers to deal with job insecurity.

2.1. Transactional Stress Theory

According to the transactional stress theory, transactions between people and their surroundings can be used to understand stressful situations (Lazarus & Folkman, 2019). Kraimer et al. (2022) define transaction as a process through which a person uses primary and secondary cognitive assessment to evaluate his/her working environment. Biggs et al. (2017)

state that workers evaluate a scenario to see whether it significantly affects their well-being through primary appraisal. If the circumstance is deemed unimportant for the person's wellbeing, action is not required; instead, the person should adjust to the circumstances (Biggs et al., 2017; Miller & McCool, 2003). Secondly, if the situation is classified as positive, it indicates that adaptation is required and that the circumstance is not stressful (Lazarus and Folkman, 2019). Thirdly, following secondary evaluation, negative feelings like fear or anxiety are triggered if the situation from primary appraisal is viewed as stressful and harmful to wellbeing (Cudré-Mauroux, 2021; Folkman & Lazarus, 2019). Transactional stress theory identifies job insecurity as a threat to employment, which provides income and social network for workers (De Witte, 2009). Faced with a threat to wellbeing, the transaction stress theory assumes that workers utilize coping strategies to deal with the identified threat (Dillard, 2019; Biggs et al., 2017; Coyne et al., 2019).

2.2. Job Insecurity

Shoss (2017) defines job insecurity as a perceived inability to sustain desired continuity in a threatened job situation. Similarly, job insecurity was described by Hartley et al. (2016) as a difference between the degree of security that employees actually feel and the degree that they may desire. Additionally, Davy et al. (2017) define job insecurity as the concern that employees have regarding their employment status going forward. Researchers (Sverke & Hellgren, 2018; Mauno, 2019; Probst, 2018; De Witte & Van Hootegem, 2021; Yaşlıoğlu et al., 2013) argue that job insecurity is a stressor with unfavorable effects.

2.3. Antecedents of Job Insecurity

The concept of job insecurity experiences can be better understood by considering their causes. De White (2015) argues that quantitative and qualitative job insecurity experiences arise from workers' interpretations of environmental factors. Kinnunen and Natti (2014) classified antecedents of job insecurity into three categories, namely demographic, positional and environmental factors.

2.3.1. Demographics Factors

Age is known to determine job insecurity experiences. Elderly people are reported to have less job insecurity because of lesser responsibility for others (Huang et al., 2012; Lavaysse et al., 2018). Similarly, Yusoff (2017) contends that employees in the 30s and 40s age range are typically responsible for raising children and may, thus, be more vulnerable to job losses than individuals who are solely responsible for their own subsistence (De Witte, 2017). Nonetheless, some researchers indicate that older workers can be more susceptible to job insecurity (De Witte, 2003; Hartley et al., 2019). This has been linked to the possibility that older workers would have a harder time finding new jobs, making them more susceptible to losing their jobs (Hartley et al., 2019). In circumstances involving employment insecurity, gender may also be a significant factor (Bosman & Buitendach, 2015; Keim et al., 2018; Lavaysse et al., 2019). The main path for this demographic feature indicates that men suffer higher levels of insecurity than women, despite exceptions (Lavaysse et al., 2019). Nonetheless, the primary that Lavaysse et al. (2019) make is that the household breadwinner faces greater job uncertainty. Men

typically report higher degrees of job insecurity than women, according to some of the few research studies that examine how gender affects perceptions of job insecurity. This has been explained by traditional norms, which require men to be the family's breadwinner, causing them to experience higher degrees of work insecurity than women (Hartley et al., 2019). But this argument also suggests that a woman who supported her family solely through her work could reasonably be expected to face more job insecurity than a man who did not bear the same responsibility (De Witte, 2019), which complicates oversimplifying the impact of gender.

2.3.2. Positional Characteristics

Barling and Gallagher (2018) discovered that job insecurity is less for full-time employees compared to temporary workers. Similarly, Blackmore and Kuntz (2017) argue that perceptions of work instability may also be influenced by possessing a certain kind of employment contract. There may be less employment insecurity experiences for workers who are hired on full-time or permanent contracts. Compared to temporary or part-time workers, these employees could feel more like essential members of the company (Sverke et al., 2000). Gallagher and McLean's (2019) study found that temporary employees experience less job insecurity compared to permanent workers. Manual and low income workers are often considered to be more sensitive to the possibility of losing their work because they depend on their income more (Frese, 2014; Kinnunen et al., 2019). Additionally, research indicates that, compared to other worker groups, blue-collar workers perceive higher degrees of job insecurity (Näswall & DeWitte, 2018).

2.3.3. Environmental and Organizational Characteristics

A key concern in addressing job insecurity is organizational and environmental factors like social support. Workers with access to outside assistance such as family support have reported reduced levels of employment insecurity. Experiences with job insecurity are also influenced by the state of the economy. Higher unemployment rates in the economy also mean that workers have fewer options for alternative jobs on the labor market, which affects their employability (Fugate, Kinicki, & Ashforth, 2014). This can make workers more dependent on their current job, increasing job insecurity experiences (Gallie et al., 2008; Schaufeli, 2002; Sverke et al, 2004).

2.4. Coping with Job Insecurity

Coping is defined as behavioral and cognitive attempts to control discomfort and the distressing situation (Folkman, 2013). Coping is another strategy for handling stressful situations, covered under the transactional stress theory (Hatley et al., 2016). Researchers aver that there are numerous ways to deal with employment insecurity. According to Shoss (2017), coping mechanisms might be behavioral or cognitive, which are more obviously visible behavioral acts. Control-oriented and escapist/avoidance strategies were recognized by Roskies (2015) as ways to cope with work insecurity. Additionally, emotional discharge, cognitive avoidance, disengagement, cognitive redefinition, direct action to maintain current job, and direct action to improve future job prospects, are the six different coping strategies that Louis-Guerin and Fournier (2014) list to lessen the stress of job insecurity. Lazarus and Folkman (1984) divided coping strategies into two categories, namely emotion-focused and problem-focused.

2.4.1. Emotion Focused

According to Lazarus and Folkman (1984), emotion-focused techniques aim to reduce the emotional pain of job insecurity. Likewise, Cox (2013) contends that emotion-focused coping methods address the feelings sparked by a stressor to take charge of the situation. Intentional actions that assist people to adjust to a difficult circumstance can also be categorized as emotion-focused coping (Rudisill 2002).

Common emotion-focused coping methods were identified by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) as emotional expression, emotional containment, avoiding thinking about the issue, devaluing the situation, blaming oneself, denial, and physical activity. Billings and Moos (2009) state that there are two types of emotion-focused coping strategies: those that deal with the issue by avoidance and those that deal with it through reappraisal such as devaluation. According to Richter et al. (2013), emotionally avoided situations, wishful thinking, isolation, and self-blame are examples of negative emotion-focused coping techniques that may have unfavorable effects.

Similarly, Baker and Berenbaum (2007) recognize downplaying the effects of losing a job, avoiding thinking about job insecurity, and expressing feelings to others, as emotion focused strategies. Stiglbauer and Batinic (2015) posit that emotion-focused coping helps to mitigate the effects of work insecurity since it allows for the modification of feelings linked to it, even in situations when eliminating the source of stress is not possible.

2.4.2. Problem Focused

Problem-focused coping method aims to address and alter the underlying causes of stress by taking the required steps to prevent, minimize, and completely eradicate the effects of stress (Zeidner, 1995). According to researchers, problem-focused techniques entail doing doable actions to deal with job instability like searching for new employment (Berenbaum, 2017), or building social networks that might result in job offers (Richter et al., 2013). Similarly, Pinquart and Silbereisen (2018) identified looking for new employment as a problem-focused coping approach. Some of the main problem-focused tactics to lessen work insecurity, according to Lazarus and Folkman (1984), include looking for other employment, social support such as union assistance, or talking to the supervisor about the situation. Problem-focused coping techniques are believed to be the best because they focus on the root of the issue and produce better results (Frone, 2016). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that problem-focused techniques to overcome employment insecurity lessen depression symptoms (Russell, & Cooper, 2015).

2.4.3. Avoidance

According to Skinner et al. (2013), an avoidance strategy entails removing oneself from the issue or circumstance on a mental and physical level. In a similar vein, Shoss (2017) claims that avoidance is a passive, inert, or disconnected coping mechanism. This coping strategy, likewise, focuses on changing the stressor's emotional reaction, but in a more submissive manner (Tanres et al., 2012).

In avoidance, employees strive to pretend that there is no issue and repress worries about possibly losing their jobs. When faced with job uncertainty, employees may attempt to divert their attention from the possibility of losing their jobs or attempt to forget about it altogether (Cooper, 2015).

2.4.5. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

According to the rational choice theory, employees who face job insecurity display extra-role behaviors that demonstrate their commitment to the company. Feather and Rauter (2014) postulate that employees who experience job insecurity may act in ways outside of their roles and take up civic responsibilities in place of seeking employment. Feather and Rauter's (2014) study also revealed that contingent workers used OCBs as a strategy to deal with job insecurity.

The aforementioned information indicates that contract workers might carry out OCBs to keep their job. Extant literature supports the idea that job insecurity acts as a stressor for workers, encouraging them to work harder and to believe that their good work will result in continued employment (Callea et al., 2016; Quansah & Obeng, 2022; Naseri & Hoshyar, 2023). Similarly, Chirumbolo (2016) asserts that employees may be motivated to participate in extra-role activities in addition to their in-role activities owing to the fear of losing their jobs.

2.4.6. Deviant Work Behaviors

Izkovich (2016) maintains that employment insecurity and aberrant conduct is positively correlated. Deviant behavior is arbitrary, unproductive, and generally seen as a response to a stressful circumstance such as experiencing job insecurity (Huang et al., 2017; Qin et al., 2021; Callea et al., 2016; Bennett, 2013).

According to Naseri and Hoshyar (2023), employees who act in a deviant manner are taking revenge for unfair working circumstances and unsatisfactory working conditions by acting in a way that is detrimental to the company and other employees.

Deviant work practices include showing up late, not putting in your best effort, and taking longer breaks than is allowed (Zandi et al., 2023; Naseri et al., 2023; Qin et al., 2021). Spector et al. (2016) recognized withdrawal as an additional type of deviant work behavior, intended to harm the organization by devoting less time to the work.

2.4.7. Impression Management

According to Purba (2018), workplace pressures like job insecurity motivate employees to employ effective impression management strategies to deal with job insecurity. Similarly, Andriana (2018) contends that employees try to improve their job insecurity experiences by using impression management strategies. The connection between impression management and job insecurity was likewise described by the transactional stress theory. In summation, Lazarus and Folkman (1984) suggest that employees who perceive their circumstances to be challenging but controllable, would initiate coping mechanisms, which ultimately result in impression management as a means of overcoming job insecurity.

2.4.8. Social Support

It is well established that social support lowers stress perceptions (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). There are other sources of social support, including union and family support. It has been discovered that family-based support can mitigate some of the detrimental effects of employment insecurity (Lim, 2015). According to Germeys (2012), having a union membership may help to shield an employee from management decisions that could be detrimental to them. Since unions frequently have a strong collective voice and may be able to alter management decisions in favor of the employees, the sense of helplessness sometimes linked with job insecurity may lessen (Hartley, 2009). According to study findings on the relationship between union membership and work insecurity, union members have less job insecurity experiences than non-members (Schreurs and Hetty, 2013; van Emmerik & Günter, 2015).

2.5.9. Religion and Spirituality

Though several studies to date have produced conflicting and ambiguous views about whether and to what extent spirituality enables workers to cope with job insecurity effectively, religion and spirituality are known to play a role in coping with job insecurity (Probst & Strand, 2016; Schreurs et al., 2014). While some academics mention that workers who are identified as religious and spiritual might have less strongly negative emotions regarding work uncertainty (Bin Othman & Wahab, 2010; Safaria, 2014; Probst & Strand, 2010), other researchers indicate that religion might actually make people feel more mentally stressed about job instability (Lucero, 2013; Probst & Byrd, 2017; Schreurs et al., 2014). Some people respond to job insecurity by engaging in spiritual activities in addition to taking such pragmatic measures (Lucero, 2013; Probst & Strand, 2010). According to Lucero (2013), employees who view their jobs as lifesavers typically turn to religion to help them get over their anxiety of losing these vital positions. Similarly, Wahab (2011) declares that some employees turn to spiritual activities like "prayer or meditation" as a coping mechanism for job insecurity. These workers use spiritual activities like prayer and meditation to lessen worry and rely on faith to empower them and to get them through challenging moments (Demerouti, 2014).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Philosophy

Research philosophy relates to knowledge, assumption, and nature of the study and ways of developing knowledge (Saunders et al., 2019). Saunders (2019) identified four major research philosophies, namely positivism, critical realism, interpretivism and pragmatism. The researchers used the interpretivist philosophy because it shares the same philosophical base with qualitative methodology that this study utilized.

3.2. Research Approach

Williams (2007) identifies qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods as the three main approaches to conduct research. This study used the qualitative research approach. Blustein et

al. (2015) state that the qualitative approach helps researchers and readers to understand the meaning created through evolving relationships and helps to gain a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences through first-hand accounts. The qualitative research approach allowed the researchers to explore coping mechanisms that contingent workers at the case organization use to deal with job insecurity.

3.3. Population and Sample

The target population of this study comprised contingent workers at the case multi-national firm in Zimbabwe. Contingent workers were chosen for the study because of the precarious nature of their contracts. Purposeful sampling was used to select participants who have appropriate knowledge to answer the research question. The study criteria required participants to have knowledge of and experience with the subject matter. A minimum of five months of job experience was another prerequisite for participation. Based on the data saturation principle, the researchers decided on a sample size of ten participants. Saturation is commonly defined as a technique that is employed to guarantee the acquisition of sufficient and high-quality data to bolster research endeavors (Fusch, 2015). Though the outcomes of a qualitative research study may not be generalized, a small sample size provided the researchers with in-depth information about the coping strategies that the contingent workers at the case organisation used to deal with job insecurity.

3.4. Data Collection

Semi-structured interviews were one of the methods that were used to obtain data for the study. The participants received a briefing before the interviews commenced regarding the process, goal, duration, and expected outcomes. Open-ended questions were asked during face-to-face, semi-structured interviews. Onwuegbuzie and Byers (2014) state that open-ended questions are good at eliciting data from research participants. A tape recorder was used to record the interviews, while the collected data was transcribed shortly after the interviews. To obtain additional data and depth on the subject, follow-up questions were asked by the researchers to prompt additional responses.

3.5. Data Analysis

Ravitch (2016) defines data analysis as a systemic process that the researcher uses to give meaning to gathered data. Data analysis, according to Rubin and Rubin (2012), is the methodical procedure that progressively advances a study from the initial stages of gathering raw data to the point of offering conclusive answers to the research question. The researchers adhered to Braun and Clarke's (2006) data analysis guidelines. The researchers conducted thematic data analysis, using the ATLAS.ti system to code, sort, interpret, and retrieve a sizable amount of data from text. The ATLAS.ti system assisted the researchers to handle copious amounts of data and to provide a thorough and visible audit trail.

3.6. Trustworthiness

Lincoln and Guba (1985) define trustworthiness as the truthfulness of findings in qualitative research, or the degree of trust and confidence that readers have in research results. Lincoln

and Guba (1985) describe trustworthiness to include credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability. To ensure trustworthiness, the researchers observed Lincoln and Guba’s (1985) measures of trustworthiness. Table 1 below summarises measures of trustworthiness that researchers observed.

Table 1: Measures of Trustworthiness

Measure of Trustworthiness	Meaning	How to ensure the measure of trustworthiness
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reality of the issue under study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Debriefing Prolonged engagement Member checking
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applicability of study’s findings to other contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thick and rich description of the findings
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to demonstrate consistency by reducing errors and biases in research Replication of study to produce similar and consistent results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed methodology description Audit trail
Confirmability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extent to which study’s findings are shaped by participants’ views, and not the researchers’ bias 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Audit trail Reflexivity

Source: Authors’ compilation

3.7. Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration is concerned with preventing harm during the research process (Saunders, 2019). Table 2 below presents factors that relate to ethical issues, which the researchers considered.

Table 2: Ethical Issues Considered by Researchers

Ethical Issue	Action to observe ethical issues
Informed consent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their role and their right to privacy
Confidentiality and anonymity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of pseudonyms to protect participants’ identities Use of passwords to keep data obtained from participants strictly confidential
Participation in the study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants were informed that participation is voluntary Participants were informed that they would be free to withdraw from participating at any point during the research process

Source: Authors’ compilation

3.8. Profiles of Research Participants

Ten research participants were purposively selected from the case multi-national firm in Zimbabwe. ‘NSW’ was utilized as a pseudonym system for the contingent workers who participated in the study. The research participants’ demographic characteristics and qualifications are summarised in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Research Participants’ Demographic Characteristics and Qualifications

No.	Pseudonyms	Age	Gender	Work experience	Qualification	Interview duration
1	NSW1	20	F	7months	A-level certificate	11mins
2	NSW2	19	M	5months	Diploma	9mins
3	NSW3	23	F	6months	A-level certificate	9mins
4	NSW4	24	F	13months	Diploma	8mins
5	NSW5	27	M	9months	Bachelor’s degree	9mins
6	NSW6	21	F	10months	Diploma	10mins
7	NSW7	25	M	24months	Diploma	11mins
8	NSW8	22	F	14months	A-level certificate	10mins
9	NSW9	23	M	8months	Diploma	10mins
10	NSW10	27	M	7months	Bachelor’s degree	11mins

Source: Authors’ fieldwork

As indicated in Table 3 above, the least experienced research participant spent five months working at the case organization. Three research participants held A-level certificates, five had diplomas, and two had bachelor's degrees. The duration of the interviews varied from between eight to eleven minutes per interview.

4. FINDINGS

The study’s findings were subjected to thematic data analysis, using the ATLAS.ti system software, which helped to form themes and sub-themes. Themes and sub-themes that were mentioned less than three times were discarded. The resulting four themes, sub-themes and their frequencies are presented below.

Table 4: Themes and Sub-themes

Theme	Sub-themes
Organisational Citizenship Behaviour	• Hardworking
Deviant Work Behaviour	• Theft • Absenteeism
Job Search	• Looking for new job
Impression Management	• Appear competent

Source: Authors’ fieldwork

Themes and Frequencies

Table 5 below shows themes that emerged from the study and their frequencies.

Table 5: Themes and their Frequencies

Theme	Total Frequency
Organizational Citizenship Behaviours	10
Deviant Work Behaviours	7
Job Search	5
Impression Management	4

Source: Authors’ fieldwork

4.1. Theme 1: Organizational Citizenship Behaviors

All the research participants indicated that one of the ways in which they deal with job insecurity is to work extra hard. These research participants indicated that the more effort you put into your work, the lower the risk of being laid off. Table 6 below shows research participants' viewpoints in this regard.

Table 6: Research Participants' Quotes on Organizational Citizenship Behaviours

Pseudonym	Quotes
NSW1	<i>'The only way to get rid of job insecurity is to put more effort at work so that you are considered for contract renewal.'</i>
NSW2	<i>'The higher the performance, the better the chances of reducing job insecurity. I simply reduce my job insecurity experiences by upping my work performance.'</i>
NSW3	<i>'My supervisors usually extend employment contracts for those with higher performance evaluation ratings. Given such a background, I try my level best to counter job insecurity by putting extra effort at work.'</i>
NSW4	<i>'Mukoma zvakaoma but kuti zviifambe unotoshanda nesimba kuti stress yebasa ipere (I reduce my job insecurity experiences by working extra hard).'</i>
NSW5	<i>'Working hard is the only way to reduce job insecurity, given the fact that our employer usually offers new employment contracts to those with high performance ratings.'</i>
NSW6	<i>'Hard working is the only pill to cure job insecurity.'</i>
NSW7	<i>'Working extra hard is the only strategy to reduce job insecurity because I know that if your performance is ok, they can extend your employment contract.'</i>
NSW8	<i>'The more the effort you put at work, the lesser the job insecurity because they consider higher performers when renewing employment contracts.'</i>
NSW9	<i>'Being (a) high performer is the only way to counter job insecurity here.'</i>
NSW10	<i>'By working extra hard.'</i>

Source: Authors' fieldwork

4.2. Theme 2: Deviant Work Behaviors

The study's findings show that seven of the ten research participants indicated that they utilized deviant work behaviors to counter job insecurity at work. Their related quotes are presented below.

'Job insecurity is a serious issue, my brother. For me, I steal from the employer so that I can raise money to start a small business. A small business will improve my financial security once my employment contract lapses' (NSW1).

'Kutonga nhonga nhonga zviwanikwa pano wotengesa pablack market kuitiriravo kuti basa rikapera unombobatsirika (Shoptlifting proceeds help to sustain me once my employment contract expires' (NSW3).

'I do not go to work looking for another job' (NSW5).

'Tobhagura masinhi my brother kuti usatoita stress (We steal in order to reduce job insecurity experiences' (NSW6).

'Kutongorovha kubasa uchimbotsvaga rimwe because rikapera usati wawana rimwe panoshata (I absent myself looking for another job to counter job insecurity)' (NSW7).

'I steal from the employer and sometimes I don't come to work because the stress that comes with job insecurity is difficult to contain'' (NSW8).

'I come to work late because it's stressful to be here early in the morning considering that they are going to terminate your contract in the near future' (NSW9).

4.3. Theme 3: Job Search

Job search was also popular amongst some research participants. These participants mentioned that they look for other job opportunities when they experience job insecurity. In this regard, NSW4 remarked:

'The only way to counter job insecurity is to look for stable employment elsewhere'.

Similarly, NSW7 said:

'Kutongotsvaga rimwe basa (Looking for a new job is the solution to counter job insecurity)'.

This trend continued with NSW8, NSW9 and NSW10 uttering similar narratives. Their quotes point to the fact that they reduce their job insecurity experiences by looking for new and stable employment elsewhere.

4.4. Theme 4: Impression Management

Apart from organizational citizenship behaviors, deviant work behaviors and job search, a few research participants revealed that they use impression management tactics to counter job insecurity at work. Their related quotes are presented below.

'I make sure my supervisors view me as in need of financial assistance. Holding other things constant, given such a background they can sympathize with you by extending or renewing your employment contract' (NSW2).

'I just appear committed to my work, and I know my supervisors will pay back through contract extension' (NSW5).

'I use every strategy available to be liked by my supervisor; once this happens, I know job insecurity experience will be over because of job related favours' (NSW8).

4.5. Discussion of the Findings

The aim of the study was to explore strategies that contingent workers use to deal with job insecurity at the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe. Themes that emerged from the study are discussed below.

4.5.1. Organizational Citizenship Behaviours

An overwhelming majority of the research participants stated that they counter job insecurity by exhibiting organizational citizenship behaviours. These research participants indicated that organizational citizenship behavior, through hard work, reduced the risk of being laid off,

whilst holding other factors constant. In this regard, NSW1 said: *'The only way to get rid of job insecurity is to put more effort (in) at work so that you are considered for contract renewal'*. In a similar vein, NSW5 remarked: *'Working hard is the only way to reduce job insecurity, given the fact that our employer usually offers new employment contracts to those with high performance ratings'*. Feather and Rauter (2014) support the above viewpoints, as the authors contend that employees who experience job instability may act in ways outside of their roles and take up civic responsibilities like working extra hard. Several researchers argue that job insecurity forces workers to put in the extra effort because they think that their hard work will result in continued employment (Quansah & Obeng, 2022; Naseri & Hoshyar, 2023).

4.5.2. Deviant Work Behaviors

A few of the research participants indicated that they utilize deviant work behaviors in the form of theft, shoplifting and staying away from work without reasonable cause to alleviate themselves of job insecurity. NSW1 said: *'Job insecurity is a serious issue, my brother. For me, I steal from the employer so that I can raise money to start a small business. A small business will improve my financial security once my employment contract lapses.'* Similarly, NSW9 mentioned: *'I simply absent myself from work without reasonable causes looking for another job'*. Qin et al. (2021) assert that deviant behavior is arbitrary, unproductive, and seen as a response to a stressful circumstance such as experiencing job uncertainty, as corroborated by the above research participants. Correspondingly, Itzkovich (2016) argues that when faced with job insecurity, workers can use deviant work behaviors such as withdrawal and coming to work late to deal with job insecurity.

4.5.3. Job Search

Job search was also popular amongst some research participants. These participants signalled that they look for other work when they experience job insecurity. NSW4 remarked: *'The only way to counter job insecurity is to look for stable employment elsewhere'*. Similarly, NSW7 said: *'Kutongotsvaga rimwe basa (Looking for a new job is the solution to counter job insecurity)'*. The above viewpoints are supported by Zeidner (2015), who posits that job search is a problem-focused coping method aimed to address and alter the underlying causes of stress by taking the required steps to prevent, minimize, and completely eradicate the effects of stress. Likewise, Pinquart and Silbereisen (2018) identified looking for new employment as a problem-focused coping approach that workers use to deal with job insecurity.

4.5.4. Impression Management

Apart from organizational citizenship behaviors, deviant work behaviors and job search, a few research participants revealed that they use impression management tactics to counter job insecurity at work. Some of their related quotes are presented below.

'I make sure my supervisors view me as in need of financial assistance. Holding other things constant, given such a background, they can sympathise with you by extending or renewing your employment contract' (NSW2).

'I just appear committed to my work, and I know my supervisors will pay back through contract extension' (NSW5).

The above quotes are supported by Purba (2018), who avers that workplace pressures, like job insecurity, motivates employees to employ effective impression management strategies to deal with job insecurity. Equally, Andriana (2018) contends that employees try to improve their job insecurity experiences by using impression management strategies. In summation, Lazarus and Folkman (1984) suggest that employees, who perceive their circumstances to be challenging, but controllable, initiate coping mechanisms, which ultimately result in impression management to overcome job insecurity.

5. CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

By providing new information around coping mechanisms that contingent workers use at the case organization to deal with job insecurity, this study adds to the body of research on the subject of job insecurity. The interpretivist philosophy, complemented by the qualitative approach used in this study, would also offer new methodological insights as the majority of prior studies on coping mechanisms employed by workers to combat job insecurity, used a positivist philosophy. Additionally, this study replicated and validated results of earlier research on coping strategies that contingent workers used to deal with job insecurity. The study has made human resource management actors aware of the coping techniques that contingent workers use at the case multinational corporation in Zimbabwe to overcome job insecurity. Knowing these coping strategies enables managers to devise intervention approaches that raise employees' perceptions of employability, which in turn reduce job insecurity. This study can also assist contingent workers to realize that some of their employment insecurity coping mechanisms amount to serious offenses that call for direct dismissal. Additionally, this study makes it possible for future researchers to conduct comparative studies at organizations not sampled in this study.

6. LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTION FOR FUTURE STUDIES

It is important to consider the research study's limitations when interpreting its findings. It is difficult to generalize the study's findings to other organizations because the researchers only collected data from one organization. The results of the study might have been different if multiple organizations had been included. The study's use of face-to-face semi-structured interviews and the qualitative research approach had its own limitations. Thus, future researchers are urged to conduct comparative studies by utilizing a mixed or quantitative research approach.

7. CONCLUSION

The precarious nature of non-standard forms of work prompted the researchers to explore coping strategies that contingent workers used to deal with job insecurity at the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe. The study found that contingent workers at the case multinational firm in Zimbabwe utilized several strategies to cope with job insecurity. The three

main coping strategies that they used to counter job insecurity are organizational citizenship behaviours, deviant work behaviours and job search. Only a few research participants at the case organization indicated that they utilized impression management to deal with job insecurity. The study recommends that contingent workers should know that some of the coping mechanisms that they employ to deal with job insecurity are gross misconducts, which warrant direct dismissal. The study also recommends that managers should implement intervention strategies that increase worker employability and reduce their job insecurity experiences.

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Author's Contributions

All the listed authors have made a substantial, direct, and intellectual contribution to the work and approved it for publication.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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